

THE LANGUAGE AND ITS MISUSE INTO THROUGH SOCIAL COMMUNICATIONS

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Abstract

The avoidance of reading and studying books, magazines, newspapers, etc., but also society's transition to fast and short reading in those of social networks and communications have started partly for informative concepts, but also the ways of misuse or avoidance. Of the standard Albanian language. The use and misuse of language by social networks is seen at all levels of formal and informal communications. The use of unreasonable and meaningless words and sentences, but also phonetically, morphologically and syntactically incorrect, can be seen in a high degree of carelessness and linguistic abuse. This study will present some fragments and analyses, but also the linguistic role of words and sentences used in social networks by our educational institutions or by various public figures and up to those of new age communications.

Keywords: Language, Media, Misuse, Social Communication.

1. INTRODUCTION

As in the first picture the social networks are playing an appreciable role or the opposite in the use and misuse of language. The use of language and social research can be used as a power of communication participation and judgment to find information of general interest, but also answers to specific questions.

Figure 1

The social search also works for finding subjective content through different opinions. Common social search platforms include "blogs" or microblogs, which we have presented in the first figure. In this figure there are several platforms where people post their comments, but written communication is also possible. Comments or questions and answers can be used in the use of language rules or even its misuse. The language terms of the platforms are mostly in English or some other language, but they are not in Albanian language, that is why linguistic innovation is created here. Albanian society and the wider society are using the terms as such and of course new words or internationalized words are being created, because those words are also being used by other societies. The communication between the parties or the company is as in the second figure as in second picture:

Figure 2

The people or they can exchange communications, but behind their statuses there can also be fictitious persons or somebodies.

Communications through social networks can greatly affect society and especially children, as can be seen in the third picture.

Figure 3

The frequent use of words and sentences can affect depending on concepts and thoughts, as in the following as in the fourth picture:

This figure proves that a person that can become addicted to social networks and then also to the language that is influenced. The social networks can have many friends, but little society or friends like in the fifth picture:

Figure 5

The research of our study has offered us the opportunity to see and say that publics or in the private institutions and various public figures often do not respect the standard language, so they avoid it. Through such writings, they are creating the opportunity for others to learn through their language culture. Our research has proven that the misuse of language is in phonetic, phonological, morphological, syntactic, lexical and pragmatic aspects.

2. METHOD

In the following, we present some publications, which have been borrowed from the statuses of educational institutions or from various public figures.

The first research has three announcements, which have been identified by the official "Facebook" of the "Ismail Qemali" School in Pristina.

All the example are in Albanian language and all of them are present in Facebook. In this social network in our country, we have a lot of office communication. All the notifications are in Albanian language and unfortunately, we cannot translate, because we need to adapted in English standard, so the Albanian notifications are:

1. *Per nxenesit e kl.IX urojme suksese ne provime! Dalshi faqebardhe!*

(Ky njoftim ka qenë dashtur të shkruhet kështu: Për nxënësit e klasës së nëntë u urojmë suksese në provime. Dalshi faqebardhë! Ky njoftim ka mundësi për ta ristrukturuar fjalinë, si: Nxënësve të klasës së nëntë u urojmë suksese në provim. Dalshi faqebardhë!)
13.06.2019.

2. *Te premten me 19 prill 2019, pritem ne vizite nxenes dhe mesimdhenes shqiptarë qe jetojne ne Gjermani. Falemnderit Ministrise se Diaspores qe e mundesoi realizimin e kesaj vizite. Shperndarja e shperblimeve per nxenesit fitues ne gara, pas mbajtjes se finales.*

(Duhet të shkruhet: Të premten, më 19 prill 2019 kemi pritur në vizitë nxënës dhe mësimdhënës shqiptar që jetojnë në Gjermani. Faleminderit Ministrisë së Diasporës që na ka mundësuar realizimin e kësaj vizite. Shpërndarja e shpërblimeve për nxënësit fitues në gara do të bëhet pas mbajtjes së takimit përfundimtar).

3. *Ne emer te drejtorise se shkolles dhe drejtoreshes Kimete Dida, urime fitorja nxenes dhe shume. suksese ne te ardhmen!*

(Duhet të shkruhet: Në emër të drejtorisë së shkollës dhe drejtoreshës Kimete Dida, urime fitorja nxënës dhe shumë suksese në të ardhmen!)

In the three Albanian notices that are presented, it can be seen that there are more than forty-seven linguistic errors only in the non-use of vole /ë/.

The sentences can be restructured and modified, but in this case, we have only adapted them to sound acceptable. The second research is of the Digital School in Prishtina, which in its announcements has a lot of misuse of language. The research in this school is for three announcements:

1. *Vend i lire pune!* (Duhet të shkruhet: Vend i lirë i punës!)

Shkolla Digjitale ka nevojë per bashkepunetore te ri ne pozitën Sales & Customer Relations Officer (M/F). (Duhet të shkruhet: Shkolla Digjitale ka nevojë për bashkëpunëtor të ri në pozitën. Emri i pozitës duhet të jetë i emëruar në gjuhën shqipe dhe jo në gjuhën angleze, si në rastin: Sales & Customer Relations Officer (M/F).

So, for to continue these phenomena, we can see on bilanguage, because in the same sentence we have some words in Albanian language and some can be by English language, like in example: *Personi i pranuar do të trajnohet në teknikat më të reja të shitjes dhe Customer Relations.*

Orari: Full-time (Duhet të shkruhet: Më orar të plotë). *Lokacioni: Prishtinë* (Vendi: Prishtinë)

2. *STUDENT HIGHLIGHT* (titull)

Elbion Redenica, 14 vjeç, është nxënës në Shkollen (Shkolla Digjitale)

3. *Summer School Korrik* (titull) *Sot vizituar kompaninë Zombie Soup (Artificial Intelligence, Virtual Reality And Health Tech Software Development Company). Përmes ketyre vizitave femijet po njoftohen me kompanitë me të suksesshme të teknologjive si dhe po shohin nga afër punën praktike dhe realitetin në profesionin e IT.*

From the announcements in question, it can be seen that they have used many English words instead of Albanian ones, then the non-use of ë, the wrong use of punctuation marks, but also the ending of sentences without logical thought are a misuse of standard Albanian.

The next research was done on the social network of the School of Medicine in Peja.

Nga “facebooku” i shkollës në fjalë i kemi huazuar tre njoftime:

1. *Te nderuar nxenes dhe mesimdhenes, urime vitin e ri shkollor 2016 - 17 dhe suksese! Ju njoftojme se mesimi fillon me 05. 09.2016 e hene. Mesimi zhvillohet ne: Shkollen e gjimnazit shoqeror "Zenel Hajdini" per klasat e X ,nga ora 13.00 dhe Shkollen ekonomike "Marin Barleti" per klasat XI dhe XII nga ora 15.00 (Shkolla e Mjekësisë, Gjilan).*

Ju njoftojme se mesimi fillon me 05. 09.2016 e hene. Mesimi zhvillohet ne: Shkollen e gjimnazit shoqeror "Zenel Hajdini" per klasat e X ,nga ora 13.00 dhe Shkollen ekonomike "Marin Barleti" per klasat XI dhe XII nga ora 15.00

2. *Si dhe ku po planifikoni mi kalu pushimet te dashur nxënës ? (Shkolla e Mesme e Mjekësisë, Pejë, 2011).*

3. *Neser botohet REVISTA E SHKOLLES –UrImE (Shkolla e Mesme e Mjekësisë, Pejë, 2011).*

3. CREATIVE

We can see the first and second research also in this part of the analysis repeated the same mistakes except that here you also have incorrect use of the capital letter.

Communication through social networks, both at the pre-university level and at the university level, has room to be completed and taken care of. In an announcement from the Faculty of Education in Pristina, they gave it in this form: Bachelor level students are notified that the degree defines will take place on March 14. The word bachelor here is used with the bigram ch instead of the affricate ç. The Albanian language does not have bigram ch.

In Albanian language the noun has five cases and the word Bachelor does not have a meaning: In Albanian language does not have the bigram /ch/, so it is possible to be /ç/ and in singular or plural it has a lot of difficult ways for to used, like with figure number 6.

Bachelor – “Baçellor” (Bachelor) Gender male	Indefinite singular	Definite singular	Indefinite plural	Definite plural
Nominative	baçelor	baçelori	baçelorë /a	baçelerët
Genitive	i baçelori	i baçelorit	i baçelerëve	i baçelerëve
Dative	baçelori	Baçelorit	baçelerëve	baçelerëve
Accusative	baçelor	Baçelorin	baçelerë	baçelerët
Ablative	baçelori	baçelorit	baçelerësh	baçelerëve

Figure 6

Bachelor – “Baçellor” (Bachelor) Gender female	Indefinite singular	Definite singular	Indefinite plural	Definite plural
Nominative	baçelore	baçelorja	baçelore/ë	baçeleret
Genitive	i baçeloreje	i baçelores	i baçelereve	i baçelereve
Dative	baçeloreje	baçelores	baçelereve	baçelereve
Accusative	Baçelore	baçeloren	Baçelere	baçeleret
Ablative	baçeloreje	baçelores	Baçeleresh	baçelereve

Figure 7

The word Facebook, like with twitter, linked etc., nowadays in Albanian language is to use as Albanian words, in fact this word cannot adapted with the structure of language, as:

Facebook Gender male	Indefinite singular	Definite singular	Indefinite plural	Definite plural
Nominative	facebook	facebooku	!	!
Genitive	i facebooku	i facebookut	!	!
Dative	Facebooku	facebookut	!	!
Accusative	Facebook	facebookun	!	!
Ablative	Facebooku	facebookut	!	!

Figure 8

Cultural institutions are not being careful in the use of language. In the following, I present some sentences that we have borrowed from social networks.

1. Starton sot edicioni i parë i festivalit teatror të universiteteve të Tiranës "E dua teatrin". Datat e shfaqjeve janë si mëposhtë: Më datë 10 Qeshor 2019, ora 18.00 salla "Goethe",... Në një hapësirë arti ndamë çmimet për esenë më... (Ministria e Kulturës, Tiranë, 10.06.2019).
2. Konkluzionet konkrete nga takimi i ministrit Ademi me përfaqësuesit e shoqatave të kulturës. (Ministria e Kulturës, Shkup, 21.02.2019). Statusi i ministrit Asaf Ademi në Facebook pas reagimeve për rezultatet e Programës vjetore ... Për mua funksioni politik "ministër" nuk është i shenjtë !! (Ministria e Kulturës, Shkup, 21.02.2019).

3. MRKS-ja subvencionon 18 federatat të sportit, me shumë totale mbi 1 milion euro. Konkretisht, sipas memorandumëve të nënshkruara, Federata e Atletikës mbështetet. (MRKS, Prishtinë, 5.03.2019).

From the examples given, we can say that cultural institutions use foreign words, such as: Starton instead of the word begins, then the word conclusions instead of the word summaries or conclusions and many other words, which are not Albanian words. There are other evasions in the notices given.

Standard Albanian is not being respected even by the various political figures. The following examples are borrowed from the "Facebook" of those with apostrophes, but it does not mean that they did not know how to write correctly, but I consider that they did not take extra care to respect the standardized Albanian:

Aida Derguti: Deklarim jasht rendit te dites - Kuvendi Kosoves

Ismail Kruteshi: Të Merren Masa për Ngritjen e Sigurisë në Shkolla.

Milaim Zeka: Takime ne Parlamentin e Holandes dhe MPJ. Si delegacion kemi gene te gjithë unik. Te gjithë e kemi kompletu njeritjetrin. Folem per izolimin e Kosoves, dhe mosliberalizimin e vizave (Milaim Zeka, 13.06.2019).

Memli Krasniqi: Ne momente si ky sot, kur po shenojme 20 vjet te clirimit te Kosoves, eshte veshitare te gjesh fjale per te shprehur mirenjohjen e perjetshme per miqte qe na ndihmuan per te jetuar te lire. Andaj, shkurt dhe nga zemra: Thank You USA!

Lulzim Basha: LIVE - Nuk ka në Evropë kryeministër që kapet duke... #ShqipëriaSiEuropa#8Qershor (Lulzim Basha, 8.06.2019)

Bekim Iljazi: O Basha je tu e djeg gjith Shqiprin. Shko ne votime dhe fito me nder e jo ne ket menyrr. Jam me PD por jo keshtu ne ket menyrr.

Sazan Papraniku · Ajde rrxonjeni sa ma parë se Rama nuk IK pa ua pague Serbi-Greqi borxhin qi e ban KryeNarkoman, Krye Mafije, KryeBollshevik, KryeEnverist, KryeNudist,...

Mondi Prenga · KY bandit duhet larguar me qfar do lloj qmimi ja vdekje ja liri

GRAMOZ RUÇI, 21.05.2019: Kryetari i kuvëndit të shqipërisë...

Bada Bing: zRuci c'fare do bohet me emigrandet , do kene ose do kemi mundesi te votojme ? Defrim Dyrmishi: Shum respekt per ju Z Gramoz je krenaria jon je ikona e historis e vuajtjeve e sukseseve dhe e unitetit te PS. Floresha Pellumb Buzi: RESPEKETE Z GRAMOZ RUCI SPS E MERITN RESPEKTIN E TE GJITH SHQIPTAREVR DHE JU UROJ ME NJE FITORE TE THELL NE TE GJITH SHIPERIN URIMR? Edi Rama @ediramaal TWEET

Kryebashkiakë demokratë! Mos bini viktimë e katërshes SB/IM/LB/MK duke nxjerrë pengesa për zgjedhjet.Referojuni ligjit jo hallit të tyre të madh e as zhurmës së tyre të kotë.Nuk ju nxorri PS nga gara po ata dhe ata duhet të përgjigjen para jush, jo ju para tyre.Ligji s'ka mëdyshje

Sali Berisha: Ndihej i knaqun qe jom i pari n'liste #padyshim

DISCUSSION

The obligation of a progressive society is that they preserve, develop and use their language correctly. This phenomenon, both for its respect and for non-respect of standard Albanian, has begun to have its identifying scope, in all spheres of social life. In various public and private institutions, this issue deserves increased care, because through their use and communication with the public, the language is preserved or developed, but there are also cases where they are abusing it. The use of reasonable and unreasonable, but also nonsensical words and sentences, both phonetically, morphologically and syntactically, can be seen to a high degree by different users.

These studies will present some examples and phonetic and morphological analysis, but also the linguistic role of the words and sentences used, as wrong by different users, who through that linguistic abuse can create consequences to be repaired or users of certain will hardly do this to recode the language. The objective of the study is aligned in several dimensions, which will complicate the work and as such are the stages of the history of the standard language, different linguistic phenomena, social networks, the official pages of our educational institutions, and then also the use of words foreign ones instead of Albanian ones and through them also the misuse of language and sentence structure.

The terminology words nowadays are to use not as English words, but us international words. In Albanian language the new terminology words are us:

Harduer, memoria, tastier, miu, monitori, printer, altoparlanti, mikroprocesor, softueri, windows, serverët, desktop, laptop, notebook, mikrokontrolluesi, wan, web-ueb, link, folder, flash, file (fajll-skedarët - dokument a skedë), start, input, output, run, license, agreement, install, segmentuesve, accept – pranoj, delete-heq, error-gabim, close (kllouz- mbyll), save (sejv – ruaj), place (pllejs- vendos), page (pejxh- faqe), mouse (maus- miu, mijuesi), box (boks-kuti), typeover (tajpouer - mbishkruarje a mbishtypje), formatim apo formatizim (angl. Formatting), klikoj, klikim, pikoj pikim; listoj listim, pulsoj pulsime, memorioj memorim, skenjo, skenim (skenerim), resetoj resetim, printoj, printim, kuadroj, kuadrim, ributoj, ributim, editoj, editim, font style (stili i fondit), getting started (pikënisje apo hyrje), system control area (zona e kontrollit të sistemit), tab stop (ndalesë e skendës) etj., kurse disa kompozitat të anglishtes kur të përkthehen në gjuhën shqipe janë të detyruara që të krijohen grupe të fjalëve për ta pranuar porositë kuptimore si: Freeform (formë e lirë), framework (kuadër pune), freeware (softuer pa pagesë), workaround (plan paraprak), workflow (rrjedha e punës), workgroup (grupi i punës), worksheet (fleta e punës), workspace (hapësira e punës), workstation (stacioni i punës), write-only (vetëm për shkrim), write-protect (mbroj nga shkrimi).

CONCLUSION

Correct use of language is a national culture and duty. This modern phenomenon is being created with a fast communication, which is not respecting the phonetic, phonological, morphological, lexical and syntactical rules, thus creating evasions of the linguistic rules. The examples we have presented are borrowed from different public profiles and of course their level is high and they know how to write correctly, but in those cases, they have made mistakes. The omission or avoidance is seen in the use of foreign words instead of Albanian words. Not fair use of ë. incorrect use of abbreviations. Incorrect capitalization. Avoidance is investigated in the exchange of ch with ç or even xh with gj. Words are used in the wrong sense. Using punctuation in the wrong places. The sentences do not have a logical ending and many other omissions, which we have presented in some examples of this paper. The notices given by the educational institutions are in violation of the rules of spelling, lexicon, and syntax, which deviations have a negative impact, but also as a misuse of the culture of the language. Care and respect for the language is care and respect for the nation!

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